

YAKUB KOLAS: THE YEARS OF EVACUATION

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Abstract. *Literary ties between the Belarusian and Uzbek peoples have their own traditions and their own history. A number of published materials, as well as memoirs of Uzbek writers who closely communicated with Yakub Kolas during these years, give an idea of the life and work of the national poet in the Tashkent period.*

Keywords: *The Second World War, Yakub Kolas, creativity, period.*

Introduction. During the war, the people's poet of Belarus, vice-president of the Academy of Sciences of Belarus Yakub Kolas was evacuated to Tashkent. A number of published materials, as well as memoirs of Uzbek writers who closely communicated with Yakub Kolas during these years, give an idea of the life and work of the national poet in Tashkent. The twelfth volume of the collected works of Yakub Kolas, published in Minsk (1964), contains his letters from Tashkent and to Tashkent, as well as the "Diary of Tashkent life", where the writer made records from March 22 to November 1, 1943 [2, 3].

Yakub Kolas with his family arrived in Tashkent on August 14, 1941. At that time, many representatives of the intelligentsia were evacuated to Tashkent, among whom were such famous writers as Alexei Tolstoy, Mikhail Golodny, Nikolai Pogodin, Joseph Utkin and many others.

Methodology. By this time, the works by Yakub Kolas, as well as another famous Belarusian writer Yanka Kupala, were already well known to literature lovers. This is confirmed by the memoirs of the Uzbek people's poet Uygun. He recalls: *"With the help of Russian translations, we have long known the work of two titans of the Belarusian literature – Yakub Kolas and Yanka Kupala. Deep knowledge of the life of the people and understanding of native nature as well as folk wisdom, simplicity and richness of poetic language – all these qualities of their works delighted our imagination.*

To some extent, they remind us of our bakhshis, who are widely popular among the people and closely related to them. Acquaintance with Yakub Kolas created the image of a wise, calm and kind person in our minds through his works. And when Yakub Kolas was evacuated to Tashkent due to the war, our assumptions about the poet were confirmed.

Yakub Kolas loved our Uzbek poets, often talked with us. In accordance with Uzbek traditions, we called him "Yakub-ota", which means "Father Yakub", and this Uzbek form of address to the Belarusian poet reflected our respect and our brotherly love for him" [4, p. 113].

Another remarkable poet of Uzbekistan, Mirtemir, also recalls meetings with Yakub Kolas: *- During the war, we were relatively young and Yakub Kolas was an elder brother and a teacher for us. And we need to remember the way our elders are respected in Uzbekistan. I often met him at the House of Writers. I remember that he was one of the active members of our writers' team. And our team was large during the war years [4, p. 113–114].*

Results and discussion. Yakub Kolas lived in Tashkent for about twenty-one months and left Uzbekistan on November 1, 1943 [5, p. 67]. His Tashkent apartment was located in a large four-storey building in Pushkinskaya Street, now No. 88 [1, p. 156, 162].

Yakub Kolas actively joined the work of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan. He often spoke at literary evenings in Tashkent, on Tashkent radio, and in the press of Uzbekistan.

On December 2, 1941, Yakub Kolas participated in an evening of Soviet poetry, on April 9, 1943, he met with students and professors of the Tashkent Pedagogical Institute, now named after Nizami, at a matinee in the House of the Red Army on June 20, 1943, he shared his memories of M. Gorky, read poetry to Soviet soldiers and students of the military academy, participated in the graduation ceremony of Tashkent Secondary School No. 47 (July 11, 1943) ...

At the plenum of the Union of Writers of Uzbekistan, dedicated to the 25th anniversary of the Soviet literature, Yakub Kolas made a speech on the state of Belarusian literature (December 1942) [1, p. 157].

At the memorial evening for the People's Poet of Belarus Yanka Kupala, his fellow writer and friend, Yakub Kolas gave a report entitled "Yanka Kupala and his poetry" on July 7, 1942, [6, p. 3-4].

The Tashkent period in the life of Yakub Kolas turned out to be very productive, the poet worked persistently and systematically, day after day, and during his business trips he admitted that they disrupted the rhythm of his writing work. In a letter to his wife from Moscow on February 14, 1942, the poet complained: *"The conditions for work are not quite favorable: sometimes someone drops in, someone calls, you have to go here and there. Certainly, I could have done much more than that in Tashkent"* [1, p. 157].

In Tashkent, the people's poet celebrated his sixtieth birthday. The anniversary evening took place in the House of the Red Army on October 3, 1942. Tashkent newspapers dedicated articles to the hero of the day, published greetings from the Council of People's Commissars of the Belarusian SSR, the Central Committee of the Communist Party (bolsheviks) of Uzbekistan, the Council of People's Commissars of the Uzbek SSR and the Chairman of the Presidium of the Supreme Soviet of the Uzbek SSR, from writers and cultural figures [7, 8, 9]. On the anniversary days, by decision of the Tashkent City Council, one of the streets of Tashkent - Assakinskaya - was renamed into Yakub Kolas Street [4, p. 113]. The poet was surrounded by warm care from state and creativity organizations of the Uzbek Republic.

The poet was extremely homesick and worried about the fate of Belarus, occupied by the Nazis: *"I remembered Belarus very often, almost every hour"* [1, p. 157].

In Tashkent, Yakub Kolas wrote the poem "Trial in the Forest" (completed on October 24, 1942) and about half of the long poem "Retribution" (begun on April 12, 1943, completed in November 1944 in Uzkoe near Moscow) [1, p. 157].

During the years spent in Tashkent, the poet wrote about fifty poems. These poems are very heartfelt, they are distinguished by high civic lyrics, and at the same time they inspired the people to great deeds, to heroic feats. Among them are poems thematically related to Uzbekistan as well. These are deeply patriotic poems, affirming the idea of friendship between the peoples of the country and, in particular, between Belarusians and Uzbeks. Kolas wrote two poems about Chimgan. One was called "Chimgan", the second one was entitled "In Chimgan". As the poet indicates in his diary the first one was written on August 28-29, 1943. *"I loved looking at Chimgan in the evenings. The clouds would hang over it and seem to increase the height of the mountain."*

That is how my poem about Chimgan was written. I sat under a walnut tree and watched the clouds". The second poem, "In Chimgan", was written on September 4, 1943. The writer later combined them under the title "Chimgan" [1, p. 158].

In the poem "At Sunset", the beauty of the landscape further emphasizes the poet's longing for his native land.

Yakub Kolas's poems were widely published in Uzbekistan - in almanacs and collections of wartime, in periodicals - primarily in the newspaper of the Central Asian Military District "Frunzevets".

For the sixtieth birth anniversary of the people's poet (1942), three collections of his poems were published in Tashkent. "Selected Poems" (in Uzbek, translated by G. Gulyam, Mirtemir, Kh. Gulyam and others), "The Voice of the Land" (in Russian, State Publishing House of the Uzbek SSR) and "Selected Poems" (in Russian, "Soviet Writer").

In Tashkent, Yakub Kolas wrote such journalistic articles as "To Fight, Brothers Belarusians!", "Criminals will not escape the trial", "Traitors", "The Hour of Reckoning is Approaching", "To Revenge, Brothers Slavs!" (speech by the people's poet at the Third All-Slav Congress in Moscow on May 9, 1943). In his articles, the poet exposes the fascist occupiers and calls on the people to mobilize to defeat the enemy.

It happened more than once that the poems of the national poet were first published in Tashkent (usually translated into Russian), and only then the original appeared in the Belarusian press. The poems "Over the grave of a partisan", "To the Defenders of their native country", "To the Warrior People", "To the Soldiers and commanders of the Red Army" were first published on the pages of "Frunzevets" (1941-1943), and "Parting" - on the pages of the almanac "Zalp" (1942).

Yakub Kolas had the closest and friendliest relations with the prominent Uzbek poet Hamid Alimjan, who was the chairman of the board of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan at that time. It was Hamid Alimjan who initiated the publication of Yakub Kolas's "Selected Poems" (1942) translated into Uzbek. H. Alimjan also wrote the preface to this book. The collection was published in Tashkent for the sixtieth birth anniversary of the people's poet. Together with H. Alimjan, Kolas made speeches at literary evenings (in particular, on December 2, 1941).

The collection of Yakub Kolas "Voice of the Land", published in Tashkent in 1942, includes a poem "Pilot's Song" dedicated to Uzbek warriors. In his poem, Yakub Kolas gave a well-deserved high assessment of the contribution of the Uzbek people to the victory over fascism.

The most powerful work of Yakub Kolas of the Tashkent period is the poem "To Uzbekistan", written on October 23, 1943, just before the poet's departure (November 1, 1943) from Tashkent. The poem was a poetic summary of the poet's life in Tashkent [1, p. 159].

Yakub Kolas's ties with Uzbekistan continued after his departure from Tashkent. He had ongoing correspondence with some writers of the republic.

Conclusion. The Uzbek people honor the memory of Yakub Kolas. So, one of the central streets of Tashkent is named after the poet and in August 2018, his bust was erected in the square located in the very center of Tashkent.

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